
CONTENT ANALYSIS OF RAYAT SHIKSHAN SANSTHA'S AUTONOMOUS COLLEGES LIBRARY WEBSITE

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Abstract:

Library website is online public image of the library. The present study is carried out evaluation of the content available on library websites of the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, Satara's Autonomous Colleges. Data was collected from the library websites and evaluated through defined checklists. Checklist are defined under the parameters i.e., general information, library services and website features. The purpose of present study is to find out the scope for improvement of the library website.

Keywords: *Content Analysis, Library, Websites, Autonomous College, Rayat Shikshan Sanstha,*

Introduction:

Covid 19 pandemic has changed the paradigm of learning system from classroom to online learning. Teacher, students and researchers are more familiar with the information and communication technology. Library stockholders are expecting the online services. College Library websites are playing the important role in providing online library services. It is public image of the library, where the information of collection, services, facilities, infrastructure are displayed. Library website provides the online services like, remote access to resources, reference service, ask a librarian etc. Content on the website is displayed in different forms. Website can be evaluated based on content displayed on the website.

Rayat Shikshan Sanstha's Satara:

Rayat shikshan Sanstha is a leading educational institution in Asia established in 1919 by the Padmabhushan Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil and his legendary wife Sou. Laxmibai Patil. It's headquarter is located at the Satara (MH) in India. The vision of this Institution is "Education to all the classes of society, especially to the downtrodden, economically and socially backward sections of society" with the slogan "Education through self-help" (Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, n.d.). Rayat Shikshan Sanstha provides the education from primary to Ph.D. through 675 schools and colleges. More than 4,44,000 are studying in this Institution. The institution has 23 senior colleges which provides the bachelor and above degree education, out of the total colleges, 5 colleges has got the autonomous status from the concern authority. Present study is carried out the

analysis of the content available on these autonomous college's library websites.

Literature Review:

Ambika & Ganesan, (2021) carried out the study the content analysis of 13 central university library websites with 29 check lists, they observed need of more effort to develop the library website. They also recommended website development the training for library professionals. **Hugar (2019)** has analyse the content on engineering college library websites in goa. He evaluated the 5 engineering college library websites. He suggests the library website should be focus on services rather than providing the administrative information. **Kuri & Maranna, (2018)** presented in their conference paper "Content Analysis of Central University Library Websites of South India". Study of 7library websites of central universities located at Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Kerala, and Tamil Nādu. has been carried out. They concluded, most of the library has Rich e-collection, OPAC, Circulation, online database access has provided by the central university library. **Verma & Devi (2015)** carried out the content analysis study of the library webpage of the Central Universities of the North Eastern States in India. They found the basic information and services are provided on the university library websites. **Mohammed et al. (2014)** has done the content analysis of the university library websites in Nigeria. They are found that, there is enormous scope to develop the library websites.

Autonomous Colleges of the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha:

The following colleges of the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, Satara are Autonomous Colleges (Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, n.d.).

They also suggest the librarian should fully participate in developing the library website. Library website should focus on information need of the users.

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyse contents of the library websites of the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha's Autonomous Colleges.
- To determine library resources, services available on the website.
- To suggest measures for the improvement the library websites.
- Ranking the library website of the colleges

Scope of the Study:

- This study is limited to the library websites of autonomous status colleges of the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, Satara only.
- Study is limited to content available on the library websites in August-September 2022.

Methodology:

Data has been collected from the observation of the library websites. The websites have been evaluated by the checklist made before the observation. Content is evaluated based on three parameters. i.e. 1. General information 2. Library services 3. Special features. These parameters are defined based on previous library website evaluation studies. Data also collected from the librarian of colleges for more detail of information.

Sr. No.	College	Abbreviation	Library Website
01	Sadguru Gadage Maharaj College, Karad	SGMK	https://sgm.edu.in/sgmkplibrary/
02	Dhananjayrao Gadgil College of Commerce, Satara	DGCS	
03	Yashwantrao Chanvan Institute of Science, Satara	YCIS	http://ycisslibrary.weebly.com/
04	Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil College, Vashi	KBPV	https://www.kbpcollegevashi.edu.in/Department/Deptindex.aspx?page=a&ItemID=qe&nDeptID=ma
05	Chhatrapati Shivaji College, Satara	CSCS	https://csclibrary.weebly.com/
06	Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Pandharpur	KBPP	https://www.kbppandharpurlibrary.in/

Table No. 1. Autonomous College Library Websites

There are 6 colleges of the Rayat Shikshan Sanatha, which got the autonomous status from the concern authority. Out of the total 6 colleges, 5 has the library website, Dhananjayrao Gadgil

College of Commerce, Satara has not posted the library website on the web, therefore the analysis has been carried out of the 5 colleges in this study.

Content Analysis:

General Information:

This evaluation parameter finds the general information displayed on the library website.

Sr. No.	Information	SGMK	YCIS	KBPV	CSCS	KBPP	Percentage
1	About Library	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	100%
2	Vision Mission Statement	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	80%
3	Library Hours	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	80%
4	Code of Conduct/ Rules & Regulation/ Library Policy	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	80%
5	Collection	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	100%
6	Membership	Y	N	N	Y	N	40%
7	Services	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	100%
8	Infrastructure	Y	N	N	N	N	20%
9	Library Staff	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	80%
10	Advisory Committee	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	80%
11	Library Sections	Y	N	N	N	N	20%
12	New Arrivals	Y	Y	N	N	N	40%
13	Statistics	N	N	N	N	N	0%
14	Library News /Events /Announcements	Y	N	N	Y	Y	60%
15	Contact Information	Y	N	N	Y	Y	60%
	Total Score	13	8	6	11	9	

Y= Yes, N=No

Table 2. General Information available on the library websites

It is observed in Table No. 2, all (100%) libraries displayed the information regarding library, collection and services on the website. Vision mission statement, library hours, code of conduct, library staff, advisory committee are displayed by the (80%) college libraries on their websites. Number of 3 (60%) libraries has provided the content of library events and contact information, whereas 2 (40%) libraries have displayed the new arrivals

and membership details. Only SGMK colleges website shows the content of infrastructure, library sections and infrastructure. No library displayed the statistics on website.

SGMK Library has displayed 13 checklists of the content on the website, CSCS has provided 11 contents on their website. KBPP, YCIS, KBPV has displayed on website 9, 8 and 6 checklist contents respectively.

Library Services:

Sr. No.	Information	SGMK	YCIS	KBPV	CSCS	KBPP	Percentage
1	OPAC	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	100%
2	Institutional Repository	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	80%
3	Link to Open Access Journals/Books/Databases	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	100%
4	N List	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	100%
5	Federated Search	N	N	N	N	N	0%
6	Ask a Librarian /Reference Service	N	Y	N	N	N	20%
7	Syllabus	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	80%
8	Question Papers	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	80%
9	FAQs	N	N	N	N	N	0%
10	Photo/ Video Gallery	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	80%
11	Plagiarism policy	N	N	N	N	N	0%
12	Book Suggestions	Y	N	N	N	N	20%
13	News Paper Clipping	Y	N	N	N	N	20%
	Total Score out of 13	9	8	3	7	7	

Y= Yes, N=No

Table 2. Library Services on the library websites

Table No.3 provides the information of the library services provided on website by the autonomous college libraries. All (100%) Libraries provide OPAC, links of the library open access e resources and link to NLIST on their website. Access to institutional repository, syllabus, question papers, photo gallery is provided on the website by the 80% libraries. Ask a librarian facility

provided by the YCIS only. Online Book suggestion and newspaper clipping are provided on SGMK Library website only. Whereas, no library provides federated search, FAQ, plagiarism policy.

It is observed that, all libraries tried to provide most of the basic library services on their website, whereas advanced library services like, federated

search, plagiarism check service are not provided through website.

Features of Library Website:

Sr. No.	Information	SGMK	YCIS	KBPV	CSCS	KBPP	Percentage
1	Continuously update	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	100%
2	Navigation	Y	N	N	N	N	20%
3	Downloads Forms	N	N	N	N	N	0%
4	Links of Social Networking	Y	N	N	N	N	20%
5	Feedback	Y	Y	N	N	N	40%
6	Website Visit Counter	Y	N	N	Y	N	40%
7	Copyright statement	N	N	N	N	N	0%
8	Google Map Location	Y	N	N	N	N	20%
9	Sitemap	N	N	N	N	N	0%
	Total Score	6	2	1	2	1	

Y= Yes, N=No

Table 4. Features of library websites

Table No. 4 shows the features of the library websites. It is observed that all library websites are continuously updated. SGMK library displayed the navigation, link to social networking sites, location of the library on map. Feedback and website visitor counter (hit counter) are provided by the 40% libraries on their website. No library website displayed the copyright

statement, sitemap and facility to download the forms.

It is found that, SGMK library has tried to develop the easy access to the website through multiple features. YCIS, KBPV, CSCS, KBPP libraries have not given more attentions toward the features of the library for easy access to its multiple webpages and services.

Ranking:

Rank	Name of the College	General Information (15)	Library services (13)	Website Features (9)	Score (37)	Percentage
1	SGMK	13	9	6	28	75.67%
2	CSCS	11	7	2	20	54.05 %
3	YCIS	8	8	2	18	48.64 %
4	KBPP	9	7	1	17	45.94 %
5	KBPV	6	3	1	10	27.27 %

Table 5. Ranking of library websites

The content analysis is carried out based on three parameters i.e., general information, library services, websites features. These parameters made with the 37 check list points. Ranking has been

carried out based on the parameters and content provided on the websites. It is observed that Sadaguru Gadage Maharaj College Karad (SGMK) has got the first position with the 27 (75.67%) points.

Chhatrapati Shivaji College Satara (CSCS) provided 20 (54.05%) points at second position, Yashvantrao Chavan Institute of Satara (18 points, 48.64%), Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Pandharpur (17 points, 45.94 %) and Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil College, Vashi (10 points , 27.27 %) got the third, fourth and fifth position respectively.

Conclusion:

Library website is the online gateway to the library. After the covid 19 pandemic role of library has been changed. The present study found that, most of the library provides access to the institutional repository through the library website. All libraries have given the links to the open access resources on the webpages. General information of the library provided by the most of libraries. Ask a librarian, reference service, federated search, plagiarism policy/service, forms for downloads, library statistics should be provided on the library websites.

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